

The relationship between leadership and Crisis management: Systematic review

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The relationship between leadership and management during crisis situations is crucial to an organization's ability to respond effectively to challenges, maintain stability, and emerge stronger from adversity. Inspirational leadership provides the direction, motivation and resilience necessary to guide teams and stakeholders through the crisis, while effective management facilitates the implementation of action plans, the allocation of resources and the coordination of efforts to address the crisis. effectively. For future research, it is recommended to explore in more detail the impact of the interaction between leadership and management on organizational resilience during specific crises. It is also important to study how different leadership and management theories can be applied and adapted to optimize crisis response and improve organizational results. Furthermore, longitudinal studies could analyze the long-term impact of leadership and management practices during crises on the performance and reputation of organizations. Through continued research and empirical studies, we hope to improve the understanding of how leadership and management can be optimized to effectively confront and overcome crises, thus contributing to the development of more robust practices and strategies in the field of crisis management.

Keywords: Leadership, Crisis, management, Management Leadership, Practices

1. Introduction

The use of leadership tools is a special administrative process that produces a strategic response to critical situations or crises that occur, which requires leaders and men qualified to deal with future risks and challenges to minimize the negatives and maximize the positives(Desai, 2018). Sufficient knowledge of how to use tools for anticipating the future in managing crises, disasters and emergencies would clarify the tools, methods and ways of working to anticipate the future correctly and then work to employ those tools by anticipating future challenges and effectively managing crises, disasters and

emergencies that occur (Suharyanto & Dwi Lestari, 2020). As well as confronting countries and organizations (Branicki, 2020). Hence, there is no society on the face of the Earth that has not been exposed to disasters or crises, until the history of peoples' lives has become linked to crises and disasters (Kaleel, 2020). The terms crises, disasters, emergencies, and critical situations agree in that they are characterized by extreme threat, surprise, and limited time available for decision-making (Alawani & Hudin, 2022). Therefore, the science of crisis management has emerged as one of the modern administrative sciences that is built on a set of its own scientific foundations and principles, but it also requires special foresight skills among those in charge of crisis management (Binnashir-Alketbi et al., 2023). Accordingly, studies in the field of leadership have become the focus of attention in all fields, especially in the field of crisis, disaster and emergency management, considering that these studies are a solid and strong base on which planning and organizational development efforts are based, and they also translate the future vision of rational leadership in developed countries and countries (Nowicka-Skowron & Stachowicz, 2020; Varelas & Apostolopoulos, 2020). Which follows forward-looking planning for the future in any society, through which it seeks to overcome crises and limit their effects, and to determine the features of the vision for the state, organizations, and societal conditions that it is hoped to achieve (Davidescu et al., 2020).

Crisis management is a prevailing concept and a strategic necessity for organizations across different sectors (Johennesse & Chou, 2017). The ability to understand and effectively manage crises can decide between an organization's survival and collapse, success and failure, or stability and lasting damage (Kapucu & Ustun, 2018). The government sector encounters a wide range of challenges that can disrupt operations, tarnish reputations, and threaten the well-being of individuals and societies (Olwan, 2019). Crises, whether they stem from natural disasters, public health emergencies, financial crises, or reputational issues, can create significant chaos, destabilize environments, and cause extensive repercussions. Crisis management has become an important field of study and practice during these challenges (Jamaati et al., 2020).

Thus, in order to counteract the crisis, factors like leadership act as effective components to mitigate them as suggested by (Fener & Cevik, 2015). According to (Erdem & Tutar, 2022), effective crisis management depends on strong leadership. Organizational leaders unite and encourage people, leaving a lasting impact and driving meaningful change. Essential to leadership are good behaviour and a clear message (McNamara, 2021). Leaders use their cognitive and intellectual experiences to create a vision for the future, guiding their actions and motivating followers to join them. During a crisis, the distinction between a leader and a manager becomes especially significant, as organizations need effective leadership more than mere management. While

management focuses on preserving the current state and continuity, leadership brings creativity, harmony, and agility. Managers may focus on financial outcomes and operational processes, but leadership looks toward future possibilities and emphasizes trust and human relationships (Purnomo et al., 2021). Furthermore, this study aimed to highlight that the relationship between leadership and Crisis management. This area of research is focused on the strong association between objective and subjective metrics (Hamouche, 2021; Jaganjac, 2020). The strong correlation between the two metrics provides researchers with some degree of assurance that they are compatible, and that the use of subjective measures in this study was justified (Haya Adnan Ashour, 2016; Mohammadi, 2020). Particularly, the recessionary environment in which the study was conducted was not successful in achieving the objectives .

2. Crisis management

Based on the existing literature, the present study has identified essential factors that endorse crisis management as a dependent variable (Brownlee-Turgeon, 2017; Hamad et al., 2022). It is notable that Crises substantially threaten safety, security, and policy legitimacy, which are core values of public sector organizations in democratic regimes. These crises can take different forms, i.e., the COVID-19 pandemic, which challenged multiple levels of governance for over 18 months, sudden power outages, ICT breakdowns, natural disasters like earthquakes or floods, terrorist attacks, and transportation crashes. Despite their diversity, all these situations present challenges identical to those faced by public managers. Crises threaten the core values and critical functioning of an organization, system, or community, as perceived by stakeholders (Altiok, 2011; Askling & Phan, 2021; Brownlee-Turgeon, 2017; Hamad et al., 2022). They demand assertive actions due to the high time pressure to prevent or mitigate negative consequences, such as the exponential spread of infections or the irreversible effect of ongoing threats. Crises also involve significant uncertainty concerning their causes, transmission, response options, and outcomes, constantly revealing previously unknown or unaddressed vulnerabilities (Ardito, Coccia, & Petruzzelli, 2021).

The study regards crisis management as a reliable indicator of effectiveness, as it encompasses both present and future perceptions of the ability to perform. Bhaduri (2019) investigated crisis management in relation to learning from failure and found that high-performing organizations exhibited higher levels of crisis management. Bhaduri (Altiok, 2011; Askling & Phan, 2021; Brownlee-Turgeon, 2017; Desai, 2018; Hamad et al., 2022; Suharyanto & Dwi Lestari, 2020) asserts that crisis management should entail the capacity to deal with both current and future issues. As noted that “current organizations operate in an extreme phase of uncertainties, indicating several unpredictable

siuttaions have not only impacted the organizations but also make them more vulnerable". Their research further outlines two facets of crisis management: readiness for present crises and readiness for future crises. Present crisis preparedness refers to a management's capability to manage an immediate crisis, while prospective crisis preparedness denotes the ability to handle a crisis that may arise in the distant future (Carmeli & Schaubroeck, 2008).

Past discussions and literature have established the relationship between the concepts of crisis management and resilience, emphasizing the need for reactive managerial responses to environmental shocks such as recessions, downturns, pandemics, human-induced and natural disasters that impact different departments of an organization. The origins of crisis management can be traced back to earlier discussions and literature on the topic (Lai & Wong, 2020; Wut, Xu, & Wong, 2021). Give examples on the previous/earlier work.

Moreover, crisis management is particularly useful in terms of providing a measurable and comparable explanation for the diverse and ambiguous impacts of crises. It should be noted that recessionary disruptions and other crises are infrequent events that offer limited opportunities for learning about the phenomenon. This underscores the importance of crisis management as a means of understanding and responding to such events (Mithani, Narula, Surdu, & Verbeke, 2022).

Due to the infrequency of irreversible events like crises, there are limited opportunities to learn and evaluate the performance of organizations and their employees during such events. Therefore, there is a need for measurability in assessing the management's ability to handle crises, given that intentionally creating disruptions in the organizational environment to evaluate such ability is not feasible or practical.

In accordance with this perspective, the literature review has identified the utilization of crisis management as a proxy outcome in research studies that centre on organizations functioning in uncertain environments with tasks that are associated with high levels of risk and uncertainty regarding potential crises (Ritchie & Jiang, 2019), where management could hardly be a measured crisis (Wang, Hong, Li, & Gao, 2020; Toniolo-Barrios & Pitt, 2021). The variation in the impact of recessionary disruptions on organizational outcomes during a crisis complicates the selection of employees for comparison across organizations (Ashby et al., 2018; Obrenovic et al., 2020).

Based on the aforementioned view, the current study identified the potential of management to provide a standardized basis for measuring comparable outcomes across diverse communities, which may not be possible using crisis management as different organizations or communities may adopt varying measures to mitigate departmental crises among employees (Hruska & Maresova, 2020; Rauniar et al., 2014). This perspective is particularly relevant in studies that use management to anticipate and investigate the potential future

outcomes of a given management approach, such as the adoption of a newly implemented crisis management change, idea, or program that involves a dynamic large-scale society.

Despite being a rare occurrence in organizational studies, crisis management has been empirically studied as an organizational-level outcome variable (Bhaduri, 2019; Kraus, et al., 2020). As an illustration, Zafirova (2021) carried out a study where crisis management was examined as a dependent variable with predictor variables, including human resource management orientation, structural orientation, and strategic orientation (Cunningham et al., 1998; Yusr, 2013).

Zafirova (2021) conducted a study based on the response of employees at the UAE Ministry of Interior who had experienced crises, with the aim of evaluating the ministry's level of crisis preparedness or proneness. The study defined crisis management (preparedness) as "the state of corporate management that foresees and effectively addresses internal or external adversarial crisis circumstances with the potential to inflict multidimensional crisis, by consciously recognizing and proactively preparing for its inevitable occurrence" (Carmeli & Schaubroeck, 2008).

Ardito, Coccia, and Petruzzelli (2021) employed a crisis management scale to assess the presence of crisis management policies and practices in their research. They defined crisis management as the capability to handle the ambiguity created by a crisis. The crisis management scale employed in their study had three primary dimensions: perceived internal functionality, media management capability, and perceived likelihood of a crisis.

It is not entirely clear what is meant by "lagged effect" in this context. However, it is possible that the author is suggesting that subjective measures like crisis management may be more appropriate for assessing the long-term impact of recessionary disruptions on organizations. Unlike objective measures that may only capture the immediate impact of a crisis, subjective measures can consider the longer-term effects that may not be immediately apparent.

This may be especially important in the context of recessionary disruptions, which can have long-lasting effects on organizations and their employees (Zafari, Biggemann, & Garry, 2020). Indeed, in the specific context of crisis management, the primary goal was to either survive or maintain the organization. Earlier studies have proposed that subjective and non-financial indicators are more vital than quantitative metrics (Pearson & Mitroff, 2019; Dikau, Robins, & Volz, 2020).

However, it is essential to recognize that the strong association between subjective and objective measures does not necessarily mean that they convey identical information about the underlying construct. Instead, they share a substantial amount of variance, allowing these distinct measures to offer a comparable perception of employees' crises during the period (Kim, 2020). In

literature the variables that may influence covers mainly COVID-19 situation, however, Ministry of interior is the one responsible for handling the situation of crisis, hence those factors that are generic for handling the crisis situations and the requirements needed like change management and management innovation are taken in this study as independent variables and the leadership roles are taken as moderator because it influence the relationship between change management, management innovation and crisis management.

3. Management leadership and Crisis Management

In crisis management, management leadership is considered the most significant driver to enhance crisis-based management practices and strengthen the organization's competitive position (Vlados & Chatzinikolaou, 2019). The significant role that crisis management plays in developing technologies and fostering management innovation has garnered considerable attention in previous studies. Despite facing significant resource scarcity, minor crises often lead to successful management leadership. Moreover, crisis structures that are considered more agile and derived from employees can provide more opportunities for management leadership practices in management (Abbas, et al., 2020; Ardito, Coccia, & Petruzzelli, 2021). Moreover, small-scale crises practice a strategy of management leadership that can bring various benefits. For instance, organizations that employ management leadership can generate more profits, have a higher chance of survival, and gain more market value (Abdi, et al., 2018; Hassi, 2019).

The study by Kim L. (2018) argued that for small-scale management, management leadership is seen as an opportunity to gain advantages over larger competitors. The ability to establish regular practices of management leadership and achieve a temporary monopoly are viewed as essential sources of long-term organizational success. Thus, small-scale management has an advantage due to their size, as they can move more quickly and have a positive impact without facing crisis management for extended periods of time (Basnyat & Sharma, 2021). Management leadership practices can help organizations differentiate themselves from competitors by developing unique products, services, and processes that cater to a specific niche. By doing so, organizations can reduce the impact of competition threats during times of crisis by offering something that their competitors do not have.

Additionally, management leadership practices can help organizations adapt to changes in the market, which is particularly important during times of crisis when market conditions can shift rapidly (Cake, Agrawal, Gresham, Johansen, & Benedetto, 2020; Ardito, Coccia, & Petruzzelli, 2021). Management leadership can provide a competitive advantage to crisis management that is smaller in size by allowing them to differentiate themselves

from larger, established competitors. By developing leadership processes, services, or products that are attractive to a specific niche market, crisis management can avoid competition threats and gain a stronger foothold in the market (Abbas Zaher et al., 2021a; Al-Hawajreh et al., 2023; Li, Sun, Tao, & Lee, 2021; Guéraiche, 2022)

Additionally, management leadership can provide crisis management with more flexibility and adaptability to changing circumstances, allowing them to respond more effectively to crises and minimize their impact on the organization (Frishammar, Richtnér, Brattström, Magnusson, & Björk, 2019). The ability to innovate and differentiate oneself from competitors is a key factor in gaining a competitive advantage and reducing the impact of crises (Barnard & Stoll, 2010). By creating innovative products or services, organizations can attract customers and maintain their loyalty, making it difficult for new competitors to enter the market (Asif, Asad, Kashif, & Haq, 2021). Additionally, being able to adapt to changing market conditions through management innovation can help organizations to avoid or mitigate potential crises. While, others did not find it beneficial and proved that management leadership has not significant effects on management (Abbas & Sağsan, 2019). From the economist's point of view management leadership is risky in the sense that innovative actions aimed at the future always confront uncertainty. The essence of management innovation is to create or establish something new (Kim L. , 2018).

But increased competition, rapidly changing technology can also cause management leadership to become more complex, thus making the possible outcome considerably less certain (Navío-Marco, Ruiz-Gómez, & Sevilla-Sevilla, 2018; Ponikarova, Zotov, & Kadeeva, 2020). Consistent with this view, Al-Thaqeb, Asaad, and Algharabali (2019) warned that the uncertainty of management leadership outcomes hampers the use of budget-based control techniques.

Bhaduri, (2019), Hamid and Durmaz (2021), and many others, this statement traces the problem of knowledge accumulation to problems of definition and of consistent and correct operationalization of concepts and use of different approaches to measure management innovation, use of different crisis management indicators, studies' time periods, change of contexts, more elaborate classifications of management innovation , determinants, more systematic and coordinated analyses. Ahir, Bloom, and Furceri (2022) warned that the uncertainty of management innovation outcomes hampers the use of crisis-based control techniques. Innovation itself can be a reason for resistance towards its adoption in organizations that aim to innovate (Kim L. , 2018), and may face resistance in its adoption by the management (Krishnan, Ganesh, & Rajendran, 2022). Similarly, management innovation practice and successful development are not easy tasks as they require unique managerial resources and

capabilities for their achievement and the maximum reaping of their benefits (Abbas, et al., 2020).

4. Management and Crisis Management

As this study aims to investigate change management and how crisis management can influence and contribute to the phenomenon of crisis within management, it is postulated that change management, as a general concept, is linked to crisis management (Vlados & Chatzinikolaou, 2019). While there is a dearth of literature on the effect of change management on crisis management. One could propose a connection between change management and crisis management by examining previous research on the effects of change management on crisis management, despite the limited number of such studies available. For instance, Vlados and Chatzinikolaou (2019) found empirical evidence of the relationship between change management and crisis management. The authors emphasized that in order to effectively manage a crisis situation, change is often necessary, but that change itself can create additional issues if not managed properly.

A multitude of literature has established a correlation between change management and crisis management, with change management having a positive impact on crisis management (Doern, Williams, & Vorley, 2019; Bartsch, Weber, Büttgen, & Huber, 2020; Alonso, et al., 2020). The successful implementation of change management is dependent on the employees' readiness to critically assess and manage the crisis that may arise during the change process (Vlados & Chatzinikolaou, 2019). Ultimately, the employees' commitment to change will not only arise from their ability to challenge the status quo and create uncertainty, but also from their willingness to navigate and manage the potential crises that may emerge during the change process (Galli, 2018).

The relationship between leadership and crisis management

Leadership and management during crisis situations are closely intertwined, playing complementary roles to effectively address challenges that arise at critical times (Aunjum et al., 2017; Choi, 2021). In the context of crisis, leadership stands out for its ability to inspire, motivate and guide people and organizations through adversity, while management focuses on the planning, coordination and effective execution of strategies to confront the crisis (Gardner & Stough, 2002; Treiger, 2014). During times of uncertainty and abrupt change, such as those that characterize crises, the importance of strong leadership becomes fundamental. Leaders must be able to make quick and effective decisions, communicate clearly and empathetically, and maintain the morale

and emotional well-being of their teams. Your ability to handle pressure, stay calm, and provide clear direction are key elements that influence successful crisis resolution (Kharabe & Joseph, 2016; Mandell & Pherwani, 2003).

Crisis management requires a combination of management and leadership skills. Managers play a critical role in organizing teams, resources and processes to ensure an efficient response to the crisis. On the other hand, leaders inspire commitment, foster resilience and promote a positive approach to adversity, which contributes significantly to an organization's ability to overcome crisis (Hao & Yazdanifard, 2015; Zhang, 2020). The differentiation between leadership and management in crisis situations lies in their approaches and priorities. While leadership focuses on long-term vision, motivation and creative problem solving, management focuses on implementing practical measures, coordinating resources and supervising the execution of action plans. Both aspects are essential for a comprehensive and effective response to crises. In times of crisis, communication becomes a critical tool for leadership and management. Leaders must maintain open and transparent communication with their teams, customers and other stakeholders, providing accurate information, regular updates and clear guidance. On the other hand, communication management during a crisis involves the coordination of messages, reputation management and timely response to changing situations (Banjarnahor et al., 2018; Khoshlahn & Ardabili, 2016). The ability to adapt is another key aspect that both leadership and management must demonstrate in crisis situations. Crises often require flexible, innovative and rapid responses to address emerging challenges, highlighting the importance of agility and the ability to think creatively in decision-making (Ikhwan, 2016; Kriger & Zhovtobryukh, 2013). In the context of crisis, decision making becomes a crucial element that integrates leadership and management. Leaders must be able to make informed, data-driven decisions, assess risks and consider multiple possible scenarios, while managers must implement these decisions efficiently and effectively (Jena et al., 2018; Lan et al., 2019).

5. Conclusion and future studies

the relationship between leadership and management during crisis situations is crucial to an organization's ability to respond effectively to emerging challenges, maintain stability, and emerge stronger from adversity. Inspirational leadership provides the direction, motivation and resilience necessary to guide teams and stakeholders through the crisis, while effective management facilitates the implementation of action plans, the allocation of resources and the coordination of efforts to address the crisis. Effectively (Alhammedi & Thesis, 2019; Duggar, 2009; Elhadj, 2013; Jena et al., 2018; Koon & Ho, 2021; Lan et al., 2019; Saputra & Mahaputra, 2022). For future

research, it is suggested to further explore how the interaction between leadership and management influences organizational resilience during specific crises (such as economic crises, pandemics, natural disasters, among others). Furthermore, one could investigate how different leadership and management theories can be applied and adapted to optimize crisis response and improve organizational results. Likewise, longitudinal studies could analyze the long-term impact of leadership and management practices during crises on the performance and reputation of organizations. Leadership and management are interdependent elements that complement and reinforce each other during crisis situations. Understanding this relationship and its impact on organizational resilience is critical to strengthening organizations' ability to address unforeseen and emerging challenges. Through continued research and empirical studies, we can continue to improve our understanding of how leadership and management can be optimized to effectively confront and overcome crises, thus contributing to the development of more robust practices and strategies in the field of crisis management.

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